

INFLUENCE OF MANUFACTURING-INDUCED DEFECTS ON THE INTRA- AND INTER-LAMINAR PROPERTIES OF CARBON/EPOXY NCF LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, two sets of NCF carbon/epoxy laminates have been produced via liquid infusion moulding, with the aim to investigate the influence of some process parameters on inter- and intra-laminar properties of composite materials. In the first set, the resin was degassed before infusion and the bleeding time was large. In the second set, the resin was not degassed and the bleeding time was kept very short, conditions that bring to a reduction in both manufacturing time and resin waste. Microscopy analyses revealed an evident void content in the second set of panels, whereas no voids were detected in the first one. Mode I DCB tests and tensile tests on cross-ply laminates showed that the presence of voids is detrimental for the intra-laminar properties but not for the inter-laminar ones, for the cases analysed. Damage mechanisms in the presence of voids were carefully investigated to give a deeper insight and understanding of the influence of voids on the mechanical properties analysed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The presence of defects in composite materials, mainly in the form of voids, is nearly unavoidable. In processes that involve liquid resin, like RTM and infusion, elongated voids form when air is entrapped as a result of the different resin flow inside the fiber bundles and in the channels between the bundles. The presence of microscopic voids in a composite component is detrimental for its mechanical properties. For what concerns the tensile behaviour, the fiber-dominated properties are found to be the ones less affected by the presence of void, whereas the behaviour in the transverse direction results to be more influenced [1]. For larger void contents, the initiation of the first crack occurs at lower loads, and the strain to failure results to be larger [2]. The influence of voids on tensile modulus and strength depends also on the laminate architecture [3]. The compressive strength of composites is also deeply influenced by voids, as shown in [4,5,6]. The inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS) is one of the properties on which the effect of voids was mostly analyzed [1,4,7-15]. Although the magnitude of this influence was found to depend on the material, the type of reinforcement, the stacking sequence and the void shape and distribution, in some of the works referenced here [7,9,11,14], a linear relation appears to exist between ILSS and void content. The studies carried out on flexural behaviour [1,11,16,18] did not lead to clear conclusions, with a large variability of the sensitivity of the material performance on the void content. Relating such properties to the global void content may be too simplistic, since in presence of bending loads also the voids distribution plays a fundamental role.

Also the interlaminar fracture toughness of composite materials is influenced by the presence of voids, whose influence depends on the lay-up and the loading type [1,19].

Although a large amount of experimental data is available in literature, the results just give general trends, with a strong dependence of the sensitivity to voids on the material and stacking sequence. Damage evolution in multidirectional laminates is indeed a quite complex phenomenon, it being characterised by the initiation and propagation of off-axis cracks which then lead to the onset of delamination and final failure. Therefore, both intra-laminar and inter-laminar properties play a fundamental role in the development of damage under static and fatigue loading. As mentioned before,

these properties are strongly influenced by the presence of voids. In this scenario, understanding the effect of voids on damage mechanisms leading to the formation and propagation of intra-laminar and inter-laminar cracks, considering their geometry, size and distribution instead of just their global content could probably bring to an improvement in this direction.

In the present work, a series of tests on inter-laminar (mode I fracture toughness) and intra-laminar (transverse cracking) properties of laminates with and without voids have been carried out, in order to give a deeper insight of the relation between voids and mechanical properties of composites. More extensive and detailed results were reported by the authors in Ref. [20].

2 MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING

In the present work, a commercial $\pm 45^\circ$ carbon non-crimp fabric (NCF, 200 g/m^2) was chosen as reinforcement. The adopted epoxy/hardener system was composed by, EC157 from Elantas, and W152LR. This system allowed a sufficiently long pot life at room temperature to infuse the panels.

Resin and hardener were mixed for 15 minutes at 300 rpm with a DISPERMAT TU shear blender from VMA-Getzman.

Two sets of laminates were produced. In the first one the resin was degassed after mixing prior to infusion (about 30 minutes at 0.05 bar) and eventually a long bleeding time (about 15 minutes) was adopted to optimise the filling of the mould. In the second one the resin was not degassed and the bleeding time was much shorter (3 minutes). The second process led to savings in time and resin waste, but several voids were observed in the so obtained laminates, as reported later on.

As already mentioned, both the intra-laminar and inter-laminar properties play an important role in damage initiation and evolution in multidirectional laminates, and it is important to understand and quantify how they are affected by the presence of voids.

Accordingly, laminates with lay-up $[0/90]_S$ were produced to characterise the effect of voids on the resistance to the initiation of transverse cracks.

Then, two laminates with lay-ups $[(90/0)_3]_S$ and $[(+45/-45)_3]_S$ were infused for obtaining DCB samples and testing the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. Those two stacking sequences were considered to analyse the possible influence of the orientation of the interface plies (0° and -45°). In the DCB specimens a pre-crack was introduced placing an aluminium film (thickness $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$) between layers 6 and 7.

De-moulding was performed after 3 days at room temperature. No post-curing was carried out on the laminates.

3 RESULTS ON CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

Specimens were cut from the infused $[0/90]_S$ panels and tabs were bonded.

The specimens were polished on both edges. No voids were found in the degassed specimens, while voids with a very irregular shape between the fibres tows were observed on the edges of the non-degassed ones, in the 90° layers, as shown in Figure 1. A void area fractions ranging between 1.70 and 4.53% was estimated by analysing the images of the edges. The voids were always found in correspondence of the polyester tows used to keep the NCF layers together. Probably they are filled later by the resin during the infusion with respect to the fibres tows. This fact gives reason of the irregular shapes of these void.

Figure 1: Typical inter-tow voids in non degassed cross-ply laminates

Static tensile tests were carried out on the cross-ply specimens by means of a MTS 858 MiniBionix hydraulic machine. An axial extensometer MTS632.29F-30 with an initial length of 25 mm was mounted in the central part of the specimens. Displacement controlled ramps were applied reaching higher and higher values of strain. After each predefined strain level, the specimen was removed from the machine and observed on the edges with an optical microscope, to detect the presence of cracks in a zone of 80 mm length centred in the specimen mid-section.

The first macroscopic damage event was represented by the initiation of transverse cracks in the 90° layers, the number of cracks increasing as the strain level was increased. Later the onset of macroscopic delaminations covering tens of millimetres along the specimens length was observed.

Each specimen was observed at both edges. In the non-degassed ones cracks were seen to initiate only in correspondence of the voids. Cracks and delaminations did not propagate through the laminates width, as revealed by X-Rays analyses. In fact they stopped after few millimetres from the edges. This is a consequence of the small thickness of the 90° layer. For this reason, the two edges of each specimen could be treated as two independent specimens. Three non-degassed and two degassed coupons were tested, so that results are reported for six and four edges, respectively.

It is important to mention that no influence of the voids was found on the global elastic modulus of the laminates in the loading direction (x -direction). An average Young modulus $E_x \approx 60000$ MPa was found. This property is strongly fibre-dominated, and therefore not so sensitive to the presence of voids in the matrix [9].

A first analysis of the influence of voids on the damage initiation and evolution may be done by comparing the performance of void-free specimens and specimens containing voids regardless of their individual void content. The strain level for the initiation of the first crack and first macroscopic delamination are reported in Figure 2. The detrimental effect of the presence of voids is evident for both phenomena. In fact, the strain to first crack and first delamination initiation are 20% and 14% lower in the presence of voids.

Figure 2: Strain at initiation of the first crack and first delamination [20]

As already mentioned, multiple cracking occurred in all the specimens. The crack density-strain trend is reported in Figure 3 for two representative specimens. It is clear that for the same strain level the crack density is much higher in the specimens with voids, highlighting a strong detrimental effect on the transverse cracking behaviour.

Figure 3: Crack density evolution for degassed and non-degassed cross-ply laminates [20]

3.1 Analysis of crack initiation from voids

In the non degassed specimens all cracks were seen to initiate from voids. Some examples are reported in Figure 4, together with the strain level at which cracks were detected.

To better understand the influence of voids on the crack initiation strain an investigation was carried out at the local level, taking into account some geometric features of the individual voids. Three “local” parameters were considered: the area of the voids from which a crack was seen to initiate during the test, the corresponding section reduction of the 90° layer, and the strain concentration due to the actual local shape of the voids. These parameters were then related to the macroscopic strain at which each crack initiated from single voids.

The void area and the section reduction are plotted against the crack initiation strain in Figure 5a) and b), respectively. No trend can be observed in both cases. This means that such parameters are not adequate to describe the influence of voids on crack initiation, at least for the cases analysed.

Figure 4: Examples of cracks initiated from voids in non degassed cross-ply

A Matlab® code was then developed to extract the geometry of the voids and the surrounding plies from a micrographic image. The code automatically produces an ANSYS APDL file with the geometry to be used for a 2-D stress analysis with the Finite Element code ANSYS 14.0. In the FE analyses homogenised orthotropic properties were assigned to the plies. Displacement boundary conditions were applied to reproduce a longitudinal load, assuming a generalised plane strain condition. 8 nodes plane element were used. their dimension was chosen, after a dedicated convergence analysis, to be about 1/35 of the 90° ply thickness.

As voids are located in the inter-tow regions, it is reasonable to assume that their shape is quite elongated in the fibres direction of the 90° ply. For this reason, a 2-D analysis was thought to be appropriate, even if not exactly representative of the real geometry. However we highlight that this analysis is aimed to understand qualitatively which is the most critical feature of a void that leads to the initiation of a transverse crack.

Figure 5: a) Void area and b) section reduction due to the presence of void plotted against the strain level at which each crack initiated [20].

An example of analysis is reported in Figure 11, where a micrograph and a void reconstruction are shown. The first principal strain field is also shown in the 90° ply, showing an excellent agreement between the crack initiation site and the peak point of the maximum principal strain.

Figure 6: Contour plot of the maximum principal strain around a void of which the geometry was extracted from a micrograph [20]

The calculated strain concentration factors for all the voids leading to transverse cracks before the onset of delaminations are plotted in Figure 7 against the global strain to crack initiation for one

representative specimen. A clear decreasing trend can be observed. This result means that in the presence of such irregularly shaped inter-tow defects the very local geometry of the voids and the surrounding plies, and the relevant strain concentration, are fundamental to be accounted for to predict the global strain or stress for crack initiation.

Figure 7: Peak strain, normalized to laminate strain, plotted against the crack initiation strain [20]

4 DCB TESTS RESULTS

As shown in the previous section, transverse cracking is followed by the onset and propagation of delamination. This phenomenon is controlled by the interlaminar fracture toughness, on which the presence of voids can have a significant influence.

In order to understand the effect of the degassing process on the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, static DCB tests were carried out on degassed and non-degassed specimens with two different stacking sequences ($[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ and $[(90/0)_3]_s$).

Tests were carried out with a MTS 858 MiniBionix hydraulic machine in displacement control with a speed of 2 mm/min. The crack length a was measured during the test with the aid of a travelling optical microscope (40x). The applied load and displacement were recorded during the tests and the mode I Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR), G_I , was calculated by means of the Compliance Calibration method proposed in the ASTM recommendations [21].

4.1 45° interface

Microscopy observation were carried out at the edges of the $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ specimens, revealing the complete absence of voids in the degassed ones. Conversely, several voids were observed on the edges of the non-degassed specimens, which are uniformly distributed along the specimen length and positioned between the tows of the carbon fibre NCF, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Voids in a non degassed $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ DCB specimen

The R-curves, presenting the critical value of the mode I SERR, G_{Ic} , against the crack increment, are shown in Figure 9. The initiation values (for $a-a_0 = 0$) correspond to the values at which the crack started propagating from the end of the aluminium film. The curves exhibit the typical increasing trend in the first part and then a plateau for $a-a_0 > 5 - 10$ mm. It can be seen that, after the first part in which the curves for degassed and non-degassed specimens are quite overlapped, the specimens with voids exhibit a slightly higher value of the critical ERR for crack propagation. This, initially surprising, apparent beneficial effect of voids is due to the fact that their presence produces a more complicated crack path and a more diffused damage. In particular, voids produce deviations of the main crack path as well as secondary cracks initiating from the voids themselves, thus causing a more diffuse ply-bridging phenomenon.

Figure 9: R-curves for degassed and non-degassed $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ DCB specimens [20]

4.2 0° interface

As well as for the $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ lay-up, also the edges of the $[(90/0)_3]_s$ DCB specimens were polished, revealing the presence of voids only in the non-degassed ones, which are shown in Figure 10. The number of voids in this case is lower than in the $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ specimens. However, in addition to the inter-tow voids some very elongated voids can be observed in the 0° tows, as indicated by the arrows in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Voids in a non degassed $[(90/0)_3]_s$ DCB specimen before tests

The R-curves for the 0° interface specimens are shown in Figure 11. Again, no influence is appreciable in the first part of the propagation, whereas the non-degassed laminates exhibit a slightly higher value of the plateau. Also in this case this is due to a more complicated crack path due to the presence of voids which produced a more diffused fibre bridging phenomenon.

Figure 11: R-curves for 0° interface DBC specimens [20]

5 CONCLUSIONS

The first result of this experimental investigation is that the absence of the degassing process and the shorter bleeding time cause the presence of voids, mainly between the tows of the NCF infused laminates.

In the presence of such defects the strain to the first crack and first delamination initiation in cross-ply laminates is significantly decreased and the crack density is higher for a given strain level.

A detailed analysis of the crack initiation process lead to the conclusion that nor the void area or height are significant parameters influencing the crack initiation strain. Conversely the very local shape of a void and the related strain concentration must be accounted for a reliable prediction of the influence of such irregular inter-tow voids.

DCB tests revealed that the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness is not detrimentally affected by the presence of voids, at least for the material and the void content considered in the present work. In fact the fracture toughness is apparently slightly increased because of a more complicated crack path and ply or fibre bridging induced by the presence of the voids.

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